

Atypical Presentation of Giant Unilateral Mature Cystic Teratoma with Bilateral Involvement in an Adolescent Patient: A Case Report

Omar Alfredo Casanova Soto*¹, Alfredo Eduardo Santamaría Martínez², Gladys Minu Ruz Sierra²

¹Fourth-year Resident in Gynecology and Obstetrics. Department of Gynecology and Obstetrics. Yucatán Health Services. “Dr. Agustín O’Horán” General Hospital, Mérida, Yucatán, Mexico. Faculty of Medicine. Autonomous University of Yucatan.

²Gynecologist-Obstetrician. Attending Physician, Department of Gynecology and Obstetrics. Yucatán Health Services. “Dr. Agustín O’Horán” General Hospital, Mérida, Yucatán, Mexico.

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Mature cystic teratomas are common germ cell tumors in young women and usually present as benign adnexal masses; however, they may present atypically and reach giant dimensions.

Case presentation: We present the case of a 17-year-old female patient with an atypical clinical presentation characterized by chest pain radiating to the pelvic region and sensation of an abdominal mass. Imaging studies revealed bilateral adnexal tumors, one of them of giant size, with features compatible with mature cystic teratoma. Tumor markers were within normal ranges. Exploratory laparotomy was performed with right salpingo-oophorectomy and resection of the teratoma in the left ovary with preservation of ovarian tissue. The diagnosis was confirmed by histopathological examination. The patient had a favorable postoperative course, without complications and with adequate clinical recovery.

Conclusion: This case highlights the atypical presentation, giant growth, and bilaterality of mature cystic teratomas, as well as the importance of a comprehensive diagnostic approach and individualized surgical management focused on fertility preservation in young patients.

KEYWORDS: mature cystic teratoma; adnexal mass; adolescent; germ cell tumors; conservative surgery; fertility.

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INTRODUCTION

Adnexal masses, defined as solid or cystic lesions involving the ovary, fallopian tubes, or surrounding tissues, are a common finding in gynecological practice and may occur in women of all ages with multiple etiologies. Their evaluation primarily aims to determine the probability of benignity or malignancy, as well as to identify urgent conditions requiring immediate intervention, such as ectopic pregnancy or ovarian torsion. Clinically, they may be asymptomatic or present with pelvic pain, sensation of a mass, abdominal distension, or gastrointestinal and urinary symptoms. The diagnostic approach is based on an adequate medical history, physical examination, and imaging studies, with transvaginal ultrasound being the primary diagnostic tool, complemented in some cases by tumor markers. Although in many cases a presumptive diagnosis may be established

through clinical and imaging findings, definitive diagnosis is obtained through histopathological examination following surgical resection.^{1,3,4}

Ovarian germ cell tumors (OGCTs) arise from primordial germ cells and share histological similarities with testicular tumors. They are generally classified into those differentiating toward embryonic tissues, such as teratomas and dysgerminomas, and those differentiating toward extraembryonic or mixed structures. Among these, teratomas are characterized by the presence of tissues derived from the three germ layers (ectoderm, mesoderm, and endoderm), foreign to the anatomical site in which they develop. They are subdivided into mature teratomas, generally benign and cystic or solid in presentation; immature teratomas, which are malignant; teratomas with somatic malignant transformation; and monodermal or

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highly specialized teratomas. Collectively, these tumors may present a spectrum ranging from benign lesions, such as mature cystic teratoma, to highly malignant neoplasms.^{2,4} The size of mature cystic teratomas is variable; however, most lesions measure between 5 and 15 cm in diameter, although in exceptional cases they may reach considerably larger dimensions. It has been described that as the tumor increases in size, there is a greater risk of malignant transformation, especially in lesions larger than 10 cm.^{1,2,3} In this context, the aim of the present article is to describe the case of a giant mature cystic teratoma with atypical clinical presentation in an adolescent patient, highlighting its diagnostic approach, surgical management, and anatomopathological correlation.

CASE PRESENTATION

We present the case of a 17-year-old female patient, single, medical student, blood type O+, without relevant past medical history or previous surgical interventions. Menarche occurred at age 12, with regular menstrual cycles of 30/5 days. No significant family history or known genetic risk factors were documented. From a psychosocial perspective, the patient was functional, without reported toxic habits and without economic, cultural, or language limitations interfering with the diagnostic process.

The patient sought medical evaluation due to chest pain of one month's duration, which subsequently radiated to the back over the following two weeks and finally localized to the pelvic region, associated with sensation of an abdominal mass and symptoms related to compressive effect. On physical examination, she was conscious, calm, with stable vital signs and no cardiopulmonary compromise.

As part of the diagnostic workup, an abdominopelvic ultrasound was performed, (Figure 1) reporting abdominal solid organs without abnormalities; however, mild pyelocaliceal ectasia of the right kidney secondary to mass effect was documented. Gynecological evaluation identified an anteverted uterus measuring 6.4 × 2.7 cm, with homogeneous myometrium and endometrium measuring 0.41 cm without abnormalities, normal cervix, and absence of free fluid in the cul-de-sac. In the topography of the right ovary, two large cystic images with fine internal echoes, posterior acoustic shadowing related to calcifications, and no increased vascularity were observed, confluent with each other and extending from the pelvis to the epigastrium, measuring 15.3 cm and 11.0 cm. In the left ovary, a 5.6 cm cystic lesion with thin wall and echogenic components compatible with fat was identified, without increased vascularity. These findings were suggestive of bilateral dermoid cysts.

The study was complemented with contrast-enhanced computed tomography, which demonstrated a giant multilobulated mass occupying the abdominopelvic cavity, measuring approximately 18 × 9 × 21 cm with an estimated

volume of 1769 cc, predominantly composed of fat, with multiple calcifications, septa, and material compatible with hair, as well as vegetations on the internal wall without significant enhancement, findings characteristic of mature cystic teratoma probably originating from the right adnexa. (Figure 2) The lesion caused displacement of intestinal loops and compression of vascular structures such as the vena cava and iliac vessels, without evidence of retroperitoneal invasion. An additional lesion measuring 6.2 × 3.7 × 6.5 cm with similar characteristics was identified in the left adnexa, although it could not be determined whether it represented extension of the main lesion or an independent tumor. No evidence of malignancy was observed.

Laboratory studies showed hemoglobin of 12.9 g/dL, hematocrit of 38%, platelet count of 425,000, glucose of 81 mg/dL, prothrombin time of 12 seconds, partial thromboplastin time of 24.4 seconds, and LDH of 289 U/L. Tumor markers were within normal ranges (CEA 2.3 ng/mL, AFP 1 ng/mL, CA-125 26 U/mL, and hCG 1.2), supporting the benign nature of the process. Based on the clinical and imaging findings, a diagnosis of cystic tumors compatible with bilateral mature cystic teratomas was established, considering epithelial ovarian neoplasms and malignant germ cell tumors in the differential diagnosis; however, these were excluded based on imaging characteristics and negative tumor markers.

Hospital admission for surgical management was decided, and exploratory laparotomy was performed without transoperative complications. During the procedure, a uterus measuring 6 × 3 × 2 cm without abnormalities was identified. The right ovary contained a giant cystic mass measuring approximately 20 × 15 cm, soft in consistency with solid components, involving the entire ovary; therefore, right salpingo-oophorectomy was performed. In the left ovary, a lesion measuring approximately 6 × 4 cm with similar characteristics was identified, and teratoma excision with preservation of ovarian tissue was performed, prioritizing conservation of reproductive function.

Macroscopic examination reported that the right ovary corresponded to an irregular structure weighing 868 g and measuring 15 × 15 × 8 cm, containing cystic yellow oily material, hair, and bony structures resembling palate with teeth. The left ovary was received in three fragments with a total weight of 24 g and dimensions of 6 × 4 × 2 cm, with cystic appearance containing sebaceous material, hair, and bone tissue. Histopathological examination confirmed the diagnosis of mature cystic teratoma in both cases. (Figure 3 and 4).

Postoperatively, the patient had a favorable clinical course, remaining conscious, hemodynamically stable, and without evidence of cardiopulmonary compromise. The abdomen showed a surgical wound with adequate edge approximation and no signs of infection or hemorrhage. Hospital discharge was decided on October 12, 2025, with recommendations

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for relative rest, abundant fluid intake, wound cleansing with water and neutral soap, and follow-up in 10 days for suture removal. The patient demonstrated good adherence to treatment, with good tolerance and no reported adverse events.

The prognosis is favorable considering the benign nature of the lesion, complete surgical resection, and partial

preservation of the contralateral ovary. This case highlights the importance of a comprehensive approach in young patients with adnexal masses, as well as the need to balance oncologic radicality with fertility preservation in surgical treatment.

Figure 1: Abdominopelvic ultrasound showing complex cystic images in the right pelvic region, with internal echoes, posterior acoustic shadowing, and approximate dimensions of 15.3 × 10.4 cm, findings compatible with a dermoid cyst.

Figure 2. Abdominopelvic computed tomography scan showing a large adnexal mass with cystic components and hypodense areas compatible with fatty content, suggestive of mature cystic teratoma, with displacement of adjacent structures.

Figure 3. Large right adnexal mass with smooth surface, cystic appearance, and contents suggestive of a dermoid lesion.

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Figure 4. Intraoperative and macroscopic findings of the left ovary. A mature cystic teratoma lesion containing sebaceous material and hair structures is observed (A), as well as surgical resection with preservation of the remaining ovarian tissue (B).

DISCUSSION

Mature cystic teratomas represent the most common benign germ cell neoplasm of the ovary in young women; however, their clinical presentation may be highly variable, ranging from incidental findings to giant masses with atypical manifestations. In this context, cases reported in the literature demonstrate that although most are asymptomatic or present with nonspecific abdominal symptoms, unusual presentations may complicate timely diagnosis and modify the therapeutic approach. The present case falls within this spectrum, standing out because of its giant size, atypical clinical presentation, and bilateral involvement, which pose important diagnostic and surgical challenges, particularly in adolescent patients in whom fertility preservation is a priority objective.^{1, 2, 5}

Machado Bernal and Acosta Mendoza described an adolescent patient with a giant mature cystic teratoma of atypical presentation manifested as acute abdominal pain secondary to rapid tumor growth.⁶ In comparison, our case shares the age at presentation and the large tumor size; however, it differs in the onset of symptoms, as our patient presented with progressive symptoms and atypical radiation from the chest to the pelvis. Furthermore, our case is notable for bilateral involvement, which is a less frequent presentation and has greater implications for surgical management. In both cases, surgical resection confirmed the diagnosis and constituted definitive treatment.

Espinola-Latournerie-Cerino and colleagues reported an adolescent patient with a 19 cm giant mature cystic teratoma, with a history of previous contralateral tumor and radical surgical management due to diagnostic uncertainty and potential risk of malignancy.⁷ In comparison, our case is similar in the patient's age and giant tumor size; however, it differs in the absence of previous history and in the surgical approach, since in our patient it was possible to perform

conservative management of the left ovary, prioritizing fertility preservation. Additionally, our case is distinguished by simultaneous bilateral involvement, which adds clinical complexity and was not described in the referenced article. Valdespino-Castillo and collaborators documented that although mature cystic teratoma is a predominantly benign neoplasm, there is a small risk of malignant transformation, particularly into squamous cell carcinoma, highlighting the importance of intraoperative histopathological examination in all adnexal masses, even those with benign characteristics.⁸ In comparison, in our case no evidence of malignancy was identified either on imaging studies or tumor markers, which allowed for partially conservative management, especially in the contralateral ovary. Nevertheless, the giant tumor size and bilateral involvement justified timely surgical intervention, reinforcing the need for comprehensive evaluation to avoid both undertreatment and unnecessarily radical procedures.

From a management perspective, one of the main strengths of this case was the comprehensive diagnostic approach, including imaging studies and tumor markers, which supported a benign etiology and facilitated surgical planning. Likewise, the decision to preserve contralateral ovarian tissue is consistent with current literature emphasizing the importance of fertility preservation in young patients whenever possible. However, a limitation was the absence of intraoperative histopathological examination, which may have influenced intraoperative decision-making, especially considering tumor size as a risk factor for malignancy.

The conclusions of this case are supported by the clinical, imaging, and pathological correlation, confirming the benign nature of the process and explaining the symptoms mainly by mass effect. The absence of elevated tumor markers and the lack of radiological signs of malignancy supported the

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diagnostic reasoning and justified an individualized surgical approach.

As the main lessons, this case highlights the need for a high index of suspicion in young patients with nonspecific symptoms, the usefulness of imaging studies in presumptive diagnosis, and the importance of balancing surgical treatment between radicality and fertility preservation. It also demonstrates that bilateral involvement and giant tumor size do not necessarily imply malignancy, although they do increase the complexity of management.

From the patient's perspective, adequate understanding of the diagnostic and therapeutic process was reported, with good adherence to treatment and satisfaction with the outcome, particularly regarding preservation of reproductive function, which constitutes an important consideration in decision-making in this age group.

CONCLUSION

Mature cystic teratoma is a common benign neoplasm in young women; however, it may present atypically with giant growth and bilateral involvement, as in the present case. This report highlights the importance of a comprehensive and timely diagnostic approach, as well as individualized surgical planning that allows effective treatment without compromising fertility. Clinical, imaging, and pathological correlation was essential to confirm the diagnosis and guide management, emphasizing that even in giant lesions, bilateral involvement does not necessarily imply malignancy, although it does require careful management.

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Ethical considerations: The patient and her family member were informed at all times about the diagnosis, interventions performed, and potential risks. Written informed consent was obtained for the surgical and anesthetic procedures, as well as for the publication of this case report, in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the institutional regulations of the hospital.

REFERENCIAS

- I. American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists. (2016). *Management of adnexal masses* (Practice Bulletin No. 174). [ACOG](#)
- II. Outwater, E. K., Siegelman, E. S., & Hunt, J. L. (2001). Ovarian teratomas: Tumor types and imaging characteristics. *Radiographics*, 21(2), 475–490. <https://doi.org/10.1148/radiographics.21.2.g01mr09475>
- III. Templeman, C., Fallat, M., Lam, A. M., & Hertweck, S. P. (2000). Managing mature cystic teratomas of the ovary. *Obstetrics & Gynecology Survey*, 55(12), 738–745. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00006254-200012000-00023>
- IV. O’Neill, K. E., & Cooper, A. R. (2011). The approach to ovarian dermoids in adolescents and young women. *Journal of Pediatric and Adolescent Gynecology*, 24(3), 176–180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpag.2010.12.002>
- V. Hackethal, A., Brueggmann, D., Bohlmann, M. K., Franke, F. E., Tinneberg, H. R., & Münstedt, K. (2008). Squamous-cell carcinoma in mature cystic teratoma of the ovary: Systematic review and analysis of published data. *The Lancet Oncology*, 9(12), 1173–1180. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045\(08\)70306-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045(08)70306-1)
- VI. Machado Bernal, J. A., & Acosta Mendoza, D. I. (2023). *Presentación atípica de teratoma quístico maduro gigante en una paciente adolescente: A propósito de un caso*. [BVS Salud PDF](#)
- VII. Espinola-Latournerie-Cerino, M. E., Kumul-Canché, B. J., & Carballo-Araujo, J. (2025). Quiste dermoide maduro con presentación atípica en edad pediátrica: Reporte de caso clínico. *Salud Jalisco*, 12(1), 38–43. <https://doi.org/10.35366/121777>
- VIII. Valdespino-Castillo, V. E., Maytorena-Córdova, G., López-Matamoros, I., Landa-Mejía, J., Zaragoza-Vargas, P. E., & Valdespino-Gómez, V. M. (2020). Teratoma quístico maduro con transformación maligna: Serie de casos. *Ginecología y Obstetricia de México*, 88(3), 156–163. <https://doi.org/10.24245/gom.v88i3.3561>